

EMBODIED CARBON EMISSIONS AND PERFORMANCE OF BFRP AND STEEL REINFORCED BEAMS: A PROMISING STEP TOWARDS A SUSTAINABLE FUTURE

Chandan Gowda, Engineer, Atkins – Transportation, Epsom, U.K.
Chandan.gowda@atkinsglobal.com
 Chris Hendy, Technical Director, Atkins – Transportation, Epsom, U.K.
Chris.Hendy@atkinsglobal.com

ABSTRACT

With the global focus on sustainable manufacturing and production to address the global climate emergency, it is crucial that the civil engineering profession focusses on reducing its carbon impact through better choice of materials. Basalt is a naturally occurring material with low embodied carbon emission that fits into this criterion. Hence, the current work explores the use of basalt fibre reinforced polymer (BFRP) as an internal reinforcement for a concrete beam and compares its performance against conventional steel reinforcement. The performance of basalt reinforcement is assessed in terms of: serviceability limit state (SLS) - crack width and deflection; ultimate limit state (ULS) - moment of resistance and shear resistance; embodied carbon dioxide emissions and manufacturing cost.

According to the results obtained, BFRP reinforcement matches the embodied carbon emissions (except for shear and deflection with recycled steel) with steel reinforcement for a concrete beam of given performance. However, the cost of BFRP reinforced beams is currently higher than that for ordinary carbon steel but is lower than that for stainless steel where durability is the key design criterion.

KEYWORDS

Basalt FRP, sustainable construction, embodied carbon.

1. INTRODUCTION

The rising concern of the greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions and the necessity to keep the temperature rise below 2.0°C (UNFCCC, 2015), calls for the civil engineering community to take immediate action towards sustainable solutions. The manufacturing and construction industry is responsible for 12.7% of total GHG emissions in 2019 (Ritchie et al., 2020), and the emissions based on individual sector is presented in Figure 1a. The buildings and construction sector contributed to 39% of total energy and process related CO₂ emissions in 2018 (International Energy Agency. & Global Alliance for Buildings and Construction., 2019), 11% of it resulted from manufacturing building materials and products. Hence, it is vital for the construction sector to concentrate towards sustainable development in reducing the GHG.

Figure 1: GHG emissions (a) All sectors (b) Manufacturing & construction, (Ritchie et al., 2020)

Recent developments in the civil engineering field involve the application of fibre reinforced polymers (FRP) made of carbon, glass and aramid. FRPs have many advantages over traditional steel reinforcements such as high strength, high stiffness, resistance to corrosion and chemical attack, thermal expansion etc. These FRPs are man-made and there is a need for naturally sustainable materials to curb the emissions. One such material is basalt, which is a volcanic material fitting into the FRP family. Hence the current investigation explores this application and its performance against conventional steel reinforced concrete beam. The average stress-strain diagram of FRP materials are presented in Figure 2, including basalt.

Figure 2: Uni-axial stress-strain diagram for steel and fibre reinforced polymers

Steel reinforced concrete bridges often deteriorate because of direct exposure to harsh environmental conditions such as freeze-thaw cycles, wet-dry cycles, de-icing chemicals, and traffic loads all of which result in corrosion of steel reinforcement. Due to the noncorrosive nature, FRP reinforcing bars help improve the durability of bridge decks and reduce maintenance and repair costs.

Basalt fibre has higher or comparable modulus of elasticity and tensile strength with glass fibre. In addition to good mechanical properties, basalt has a high chemical and thermal stability, good thermal insulation, electrical and sound properties (Technobasalt, 2004). The thermal insulation is three times greater than asbestos. Due to good insulating properties, it can be used for fire protection. Furthermore, basalt has ten times better electrical characteristic insulation than glass fibres. It also has better chemical resistance, particularly in alkaline environment (Urbanski et al., 2013). BFRP bars are an alternative to conventional steel reinforced concrete members in corrosive environments.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

The experimental performance of basalt FRP as internal reinforcement for transportation infrastructure was explored in Patnaik, (2009). Moment resistances was found to be in very good agreement with the analytical prediction according to ACI440.1R-06, (2006) with a ductile behaviour. Banibayat & Patnaik, (2015) carried out tests on basalt FRP bars by applying sustained loads in alkaline solution at an elevated temperature to accelerate and understand the long-term creep behaviour. The creep coefficients were determined to be 18% for 50-year service life and 28% for 5-year service life, and the one-million-hour creep coefficient was estimated to be 13%.

Patnaik & Banibayat, (2012) investigated the mechanical properties of BFRP bars to check if they are suitable for reinforced concrete applications. The tests confirmed high average tensile strength, acceptable rupture strain and average elasticity comparable with glass FRP bars. Serbescu et al., (2014) explored performance of basalt FRP bars for 1000h in different alkaline environments (pH7, pH9 and pH13) and multiple temperatures (20°C, 40°C and 60°C) to understand the long-term durability performance. Temperature was found to be the parameter most affecting the degradation process and the lowest strength retention of 69% was observed for bars in pH solution at 60°C for 5000h. Similar investigation on mechanical properties was also carried out in Elgabbas et al., (2013) and Elgabbas et al., (2015).

Urbanski et al., (2013), Lapko & Urbański, (2015) and Lapko & Urbański, (2015) performed experimental tests with basalt as internal reinforcement and a hybrid combination of basalt and steel reinforcements, to study the effect of reinforcement ratio on flexural behaviour. Beams with only BFRP had better performance with high reinforcement ratio. The hybrid combination had reduced deflection, reduced crack widths and increased load carrying capacity (10%). The results were validated by theoretical calculations. It also involved application of digital image correlation (DIC) to better understand the cracking process of BFRP reinforced beams.

Bond durability of basalt FRP bars embedded in normal and aggressive environments is investigated in Hassan et al., (2016), Vincent et al., (2013) and Mehany et al., (2022). Ribbed BFRP bars in flexural behaviour of concrete beams is explored in Elgabbas et al., (2017) and experimental testing of concrete bridge deck slabs under concentrated loads is investigated in Elgabbas et al., (2016).

3. MATERIAL AND GEOMETRIC PROPERTIES

The investigation in this paper involves three beams with a cross section of 300mm x 200mm and steel (Beam 1) and BFRP (Beam 2 and 3) as the internal longitudinal reinforcements. Beam 1 (steel) and beam 2 (BFRP) have similar reinforcement ratio, where as beam 3 is with increased BFRP reinforcement ratio (bottom longitudinal). All beams are 2700mm long and are as shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3: Beam sectional properties

The concrete has a compressive strength, f_{cm} of 44.7 MPa, modulus of elasticity, E_c of 34.5 GPa and a tensile strength, f_t of 3.13 MPa. The steel has an yield value, f_y of 450 MPa, modulus of elasticity, E_s of 200 GPa and yield strain, ϵ_y of 0.002, and the BFRP has a tensile strength, f_{ft} of 1724 MPa, modulus of elasticity, E_f of 64.80 GPa and ultimate strain, ϵ_{fi} of 0.0266. The material properties are experimentally tested and adopted from the literature review (Elgabbas et al., 2017).

Standards for the design and assessment of basalt fibre reinforced polymer are not currently available due to limited investigation of their behaviour. However, basalt FRP is similar to glass FRP in terms of mechanical properties and durability. The new generation Eurocode 2 (preDRAFT, 2021) includes the design details for carbon and glass FRP as internal reinforcement in Annex JA and for strengthening of concrete structures in Annex J. Hence, Eurocode 2 has been used in this work to explore the performance of BFRP reinforced beams. The geometric and material properties are adopted from the reference for ease of comparison with the analytical results, as well as to assess the predictive performance of the new generation Eurocode 2 (preDRAFT, 2021) on FRP materials.

4. SLS & ULS PERFORMANCE

4.1. Introduction

This section describes the performance of basalt FRP at the serviceability limit state and ultimate limit state in terms of crack width, deflection, moment of resistance and shear resistance.

4.2. Serviceability limit state

4.2.1. Crack width

Wider crack widths are permitted for BFRP than steel reinforcement because BFRP does not corrode. The conventional reinforced beam 1 (2 ϕ steel) has a limiting moment of 31.4 kN.m for an SLS crack width limit of 0.3mm. Beam 2 with BFRP reinforcement has a limiting moment of 22.8 kN.m for an SLS crack width limit of 0.4mm (higher limit for FRP materials). The limiting moment of beam 2 (2 ϕ BFRP) is reduced to 72.6% of beam 1 at the crack width limit due to the lower modulus of elasticity of the BFRP, which is one third of steel E_s . Hence, beam 3 (3 ϕ BFRP) is with increased reinforcement ratio resulting in higher limiting moment of 31.0 kN.m at the crack width limit of 0.4mm, matching beam 1 (steel). Table 1 shows the crack width values of the three beams at different moments.

Table 1: Comparison of crack width values of all beams

Beam 1 (Steel 2 ϕ)		Beam 2 (BFRP 2 ϕ)			Beam 3 (BFRP 3 ϕ)		
Moment (kN.m)	CW (mm)	Moment (kN.m)	CW (mm)	Diff. wrt. Beam 1	Moment (kN.m)	CW (mm)	Diff. wrt. Beam 1
12.20	0.000	12.50	0.000		12.50	0.008	
15.00	0.044	15.00	0.097		15.00	0.061	
20.00	0.122	20.00	0.292	+ 139%	20.00	0.168	+ 38%
30.00	0.278	22.80	0.400		27.28	0.323	
31.40	0.300	27.28	0.576		31.00	0.401	
32.89	0.324	32.90	0.795	+ 146%	32.90	0.443	+ 37%
38.75	0.415	41.26	1.121		41.26	0.622	
					60.41	1.031	

The evolution of crack width against flexural moment is presented in Figure 4a, and its comparison against experimental results in Figure 4b. The analytical results are comparable but not in good agreement with the experimental results. The experimental results show a lower stiffness in the initial zone, and an increase at the end. An abnormal dip is also observed in the central zone in BFRP beams.

Figure 4: Crack width evolution of all beams

4.2.2. Deflection

Figure 5 shows the moment vs. deflection of all three beams. Beam 1 (steel 2 ϕ) has a stiffer response after cracking moment. Whereas, BFRP beams have higher deflection after cracking as the effective cracked section in resisting the applied force is reduced due to lower modular ratio.

Figure 5: Deflection vs. moment

The analytical results are in agreement with the experimental results. If the experimental results are cleaned for the noise (initial adjustments), the results will improve further. The values of deflection at different moments are tabulated in Table 2.

Table 2: Comparison of deflection

Beam 1 (Steel 2 ϕ)		Beam 2 (BFRP 2 ϕ)			Beam 3 (BFRP 3 ϕ)		
Moment (kN.m)	Deflection (mm)	Moment (kN.m)	Deflection (mm)	Diff. wrt. Beam 1	Moment (kN.m)	Deflection (mm)	Diff. wrt. Beam 1
12.44	0.487	12.44	0.487	-	12.44	0.487	-
12.44	2.375	12.44	5.589	135%	12.44	3.847	62%
18.00	3.438	18.00	8.090	135%	18.00	5.569	62%
25.00	4.775	25.00	11.236	135%	25.00	7.734	62%
32.89	6.284	27.27	12.259	-	27.28	8.440	-
38.75	7.402	38.75	17.416	135%	38.75	11.988	62%
					60.418	18.692	-

4.3. Ultimate limite state

4.3.1. Moment of resistance

The moment of resistance for beams 1, 2 and 3 are derived for multiple compressive strengths of concrete and are presented in Figure 6a. Beam 1 (Steel 2 ϕ) has moment of resistance 32.89 kN.m and beam 2 (BFRP 2 ϕ) has a resistance of 27.27 kN.m, 17% lower than beam 1. Beam 3 (BFRP 3 ϕ) has a resistance of 39.76 kN.m, 20.8% higher than beam 1 for concrete with compressive strength of 44.7 MPa.

a. Analytical results

b. Analytical and experimental results

Figure 6: Moment of resistance against compressive strength

Comparing the analytical results, without the material partial factors, with experimental results, beam 1 with steel reinforcement is found to be close to the experimental value as expected: 41.26 kN.m (analytical) and 38.75 kN.m (experimental). Whereas, beam 2 has a difference of 72.3% with 41.26 kN.m (analytical) and 71.09 kN.m (experimental), and beam 3 has 50.6% difference with 60.42 kN.m (analytical) and 91.03 kN.m (experimental). The higher difference in analytical and experimental values of basalt reinforced beams is due to the reduced tensile strength which is allowed within the Eurocode 2 (preDRAFT, 2021). Even though the tensile strength of basalt FRP is four times higher than steel, the characteristic (and design) value includes multiple influence factors for temperature, service life and environmental attack, reducing the characteristic value to 24.5% of its ultimate tensile strength according to Equation 2. If we consider the material safety factor, then the design value further reduces to 16.3% of its ultimate tensile strength according to Equation 1.

$$f_{ftd} = \frac{f_{ftk,100a}}{\gamma_{FRP}}$$

Equation 1

$$f_{ftk,100a} = C_t C_c C_e f_{ftk0}$$

Equation 2

C_t = influence factor for temperature
 C_c = influence factor for service life
 C_e = influence factor for environmental attack

Figure 7 Design stress-strain diagram for FRP reinforcement (Eurocode 2 (preDRAFT, 2021))

Analysing the impact on moment of resistance by excluding influence factors on temperature, service life and environmental attack, and material partial factors is shown in Figure 8. In BFRP beam 2 (2φ), the analytical value is 102% higher than the experimental value and in BFRP beam 3 (3φ), the analytical value is 109% higher than the experimental value. On an average there is an increase in moment of resistance by more than 100% when influence factors and material safety factors are excluded, and an under prediction in moment of resistance when considering them. This shows the importance and requirement of further investigations in analytical FRP formulations.

Figure 8: BFRP beam performance excluding influence factors

4.3.2. Shear resistance

The minimum shear resistance ($\tau_{Rdc,min}$) of beams with basalt FRP reinforcement is calculated using Equation 3, from Annex JA Eurocode 2 (preDRAFT, 2021). It is dependent on the concrete properties and the modular ratio (modulus of elasticity between BFRP and steel) under the square root. As a result, BFRP reinforced beams will always result in lower minimum shear resistance than steel reinforced beams as the basalt FRP modulus of elasticity, E_{FR} , is lower than steel, E_s , as shown in Figure 10.

$$\tau_{Rdc,min} = \frac{0.29}{\gamma_c} \sqrt{f_{ck} \frac{E_{FR}}{E_s} \frac{d_{dg}}{d}} \quad \text{Equation 3}$$

E_{FR} = design value of modulus of elasticity of FRP-reinforcement, d_{dg} = aggregate size

Figure 9: Minimum shear resistance, $\tau_{Rdc,min}$

The shear resistance of beam 1 is evaluated according to Equation 4, which considers only the contribution of steel reinforcement. In case of basalt beams 2 and 3, it is calculated according to Equation 5 considering the contribution of both concrete ($\tau_{Rd,c}$) and the FRP. In spite of this, BFRP reinforced beams result in lower shear resistance due to the strain limitation imposed on FRP materials ($f_{FRd} = \min(0.004 * E_f; f_{td})$). The shear resistances of beam 1, 2 and 3 are shown in Figure 10, and the values are presented in Table 3.

	$\tau_{Rd,sy} = \rho_w f_{ywd} \cot \theta$	Equation 4
	$\tau_{Rd,f} = \tau_{Rd,c} + \rho_w f_{FRd} \cot \theta \leq 0.17 f_{cd}$	Equation 5
	$\tau_{Rd,c} = \frac{0.66}{\gamma_v} \left(100 \rho_l f_{ck} \frac{d_{dg}}{d} \right)^{\frac{1}{3}} \geq \tau_{Rdc,min}$	Equation 6

$\tau_{Rd,sy}$ = shear resistance of steel RC beam, ρ_w = steel shear reinforcement ratio = $A_{sw}/(b_w * s)$, ρ_l = longitudinal reinforcement ratio, γ_v = partial factor for shear and punching resistance without shear reinforcement

Table 3: Shear values of beam 1, 2 and 3

Beam 1 (Steel 2φ)		Beam 2 (BFRP 2φ)			Beam 3 (BFRP 3φ)		
Moment (kN.m)	$\tau_{Rd,s}$ (MPa)	Moment (kN.m)	$\tau_{Rd,f}$ (MPa)	Diff. wrt. Beam 1	Moment (kN.m)	$\tau_{Rd,f}$ (MPa)	Diff. wrt. Beam 1
15.00	3.073	15.00	2.281	-26%	15.00	2.317	-25%
20.00	3.073	20.00	2.329	-24%	20.00	2.372	-23%
30.00	3.073	30.00	2.395	-22%	30.00	2.447	-20%
44.70	3.073	44.70	2.462	-20%	44.70	2.523	-18%
49.00	3.073	49.00	2.478	-19%	49.00	2.542	-17%

a. Analytical results, $\tau_{Rd,s}$ & $\tau_{Rd,f}$

b. Analytical results, $\tau_{Rd,c}$

Figure 10: Shear resistance

5. EMBODIED CARBON EMISSIONS & MANUFACTURING COST

The embodied carbon (EC) emission calculations for each beam is calculated considering the EC values of recycled steel. According to the ICE database (Institution of Civil Engineers, 2023), the EC of recycled steel is 0.980 EcCO₂/kg, and that of normal steel is 1.200 EcCO₂/kg. Concrete has an average value of 0.103 EcCO₂/kg, and according to reference (Pavlović et al., 2022) BFRP has 22% lower EcCO₂/kg than recycled steel leading to 0.764 EcCO₂/kg.

It should be noted that different basalt FRP producers have different environmental product declarations (EPD) based on the availability of raw materials, transportation, manufacturing method and delivery which results in varying EC values. Hence, based on the reference (Pavlović et al., 2022) the value of 0.764 EcCO₂/kg will be adopted in the current calculations as being representative for the U.K.

Table 4 shows the EC values of all the beams, and the performance of BFRP beams (2 & 3) assessed against steel RC beam.

Beam 2 with similar reinforcement ratio as steel RC beam (1) has lower performance across all criteria. Whereas, beam 3 with increased BFRP reinforcement ratio has better performance than beam 1 in moment of resistance and almost matches the crack width limit with a difference of 1.27%. In shear resistance, both the BFRP beams have lower values due to the reasons described in section 4.3.2. Generally, FRP materials are weaker in shear as the fibres are not effective in the transverse direction, resulting in reduced dowel action and aggregate interlock. This results in wider and deeper diagonal cracks leading to early failure of the element. Additionally, unlike steel, a yield plateau is not available in FRPs as they are linear elastic materials (Figure 2).

Table 4: Embodied carbon emission calculations considering recycled steel (0.980 EcCO₂/kg)

Description	Beam 1 (Steel 2φ)		Beam 2 (BFRP 2φ)		Beam 3 (BFRP 3φ)	
	Embodied Carbon (kg's)	Percentage EC	Embodied Carbon (kg's)	Percentage EC	Embodied Carbon (kg's)	Percentage EC
Concrete EC	39.19	59.49%	39.19	65.32%	39.19	62.35%
Basalt FRP EC	-	-	20.81	34.68%	23.67	37.65%
Steel EC	26.69	40.51%	-	-	-	-
Total EC	65.88	100%	60.00	100%	62.86	100%
Difference in EC wrt. steel RC beam	-	-	5.88	8.93%	3.02	4.59%
Moment of resistance (kN.m)	32.90		27.28	-17.09%	39.76	20.86%
Shear resistance, τ _{Rdc} (MPa)	0.59	-	0.43	-28.30%	0.49	-17.92%
Shear resistance, τ _{Rd,s} & τ _{Rd,f} (MPa)	3.07	-	2.46	-19.90%	2.52	-17.89%
Moment at crack width SLS limit	31.40	-	22.80	-27.39%	31.00	-1.27%
Moment at deflection SLS limit	32.90*	-	24.00	-27.05%	35.00	6.38%

Deflection limit = Span/250 = 10.8mm, *moment of resistance attained at 6.3mm

Table 5, shows the results of varying the embodied carbon emissions for different concrete strengths (lower and higher). Lowering the EC of concrete results in a higher percentage of BFRP and thereby higher EC savings are observed and vice versa.

Table 5 EC emissions for different concrete with recycled steel values

Concrete, EcCO ₂ /kg	Beam 1 (Steel 2φ), EcCO _{2e}	Beam 2* (BFRP 2φ), Percentage savings EcCO _{2e}	Beam 3 (BFRP 3φ), Percentage savings EcCO _{2e}
0.063	50.66	11.59%	5.94%
0.103	65.88	8.91%	4.57%
0.161	87.85	6.68%	3.42%

*performance does not match or exceed Beam 1 (steel 2φ) performance

Table 6 presents the differences in embodied carbon values of basalt reinforced beam matching the specific performance of the steel RC beam. The results show that the basalt FRP material has good performance in moment of resistance and in limiting the crack width at SLS limit.

Table 6: Comparison of embodied carbon matching recycled steel values

Description	Steel beam	Steel EcCO _{2e} (kg)	Equivalent BFRP EcCO _{2e} (kg)	BFRP EcCO _{2e} difference	EC percentage	Remarks (wrt steel beam 1)
Moment of resistance (kN.m)	32.90	26.69	22.25	4.44	5.05%	Increasing longitudinal BFRP bars to 2.5
Shear resistance, τ _{Rdc} (MPa)	0.59	26.69	30.84	-4.15	-4.72%	Increasing longitudinal BFRP bars to 5.5
Shear resistance, τ _{Rd,s} & τ _{Rd,f} (MPa)	3.07	26.69	26.25	0.44	0.50%	Reduce stirrup spacing by 21.5% to 78.5mm
Moment at crack width SLS limit	31.40	26.69	23.68	3.01	3.42%	Increasing longitudinal BFRP bars to 3.0
Moment at deflection (32.90 kN.m) SLS limit	32.90	26.69	29.41	-2.72	-3.09%	Increasing longitudinal BFRP bars to 5.0

Concrete EcCO_{2e} for the current beam is 39.19 kgs

6. CONCLUSIONS

Basalt FRP bars are promising high strength linear elastic materials, which can be used as internal reinforcement in concrete structures. They are natural polymers which are sustainable and eco-friendly with respect to other FRPs like carbon, glass and aramid. As described in section 1, BFRP has been explored in a small number of R&D investigations, including long term effects.

Based on the current investigation the following conclusions are obtained:

- In terms of crack width, basalt reinforced beam (3ϕ) with higher reinforcement ratio meets the required crack width limits at the same moment as beam 1,
- Beam 3 also matches the performance of beam 1 in moment of resistance,
- In deflection, both the BFRP reinforced beams have higher deflection due to lower modulus of elasticity,
- BFRP is not best-suited for shear reinforcement as the resistance of FRP rebars are low in transverse direction,
- Eurocode 2 makes reasonable predictions of strength for BFRP reinforced elements with factors. The design tensile strength is underestimated due to lack of uncertainties and long term data on material behaviour, which is viable for basalt. If material factor and influence factors are eliminated for short-term assessment, there is over prediction (e.g., moment of resistance),
- The advantages and savings over embodied carbon emissions is good with respect to recycled steel and improves with normal steel,
- Cost of manufacturing a BFRP beam is currently high due to costs associated with the production of basalt rebars with respect to ordinary carbon steel, but is lower than that for stainless steel where durability is the key design criterion.

Overall, the performance of BFRP beam (3) with higher reinforcement ratio matches the conventional steel reinforced beam in moment of resistance, crack width and embodied carbon emissions. The EC savings presented in the current investigation is for a beam of an average size; the savings will be significant if basalt FRP is explored in large scale construction. More manufacturing will lead to lower costs in future, and the combination of embodied carbon savings together with cost will eventually be very effective and a strong sustainable solution.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare that they have no conflicts of interest associated with the work presented in this paper.

DATA AVAILABILITY

All necessary data is presented in this paper.